

Malta

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Malta, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Maltese higher education system comprises of several institutions which are public or privately owned and which offer home-grown or third-party qualifications at ISCED 5-8 on the Malta Qualifications Framework (MQF). Entry into first-cycle higher education programmes (MQF5 or 6) generally requires a qualification at MQF4 (ISCED4) while entry into second- and third-cycle programmes generally require a first- and/or second-cycle degree respectively. However, some programmes allow maturity clauses for persons over a certain age threshold who demonstrate the aptitude to follow the course with success.

Four institutions are publicly funded educational institutions providing higher education courses and are all included in the ETER data collection: the University of Malta, the Malta College of Arts Science and Technology (MCAST), the Institute of Tourism Studies (ITS) and the Institute for Education (IFE). The Maltese higher education system also comprises of private institutions offering tertiary education, three of them are included in the ETER data collections since 2020². These are the Idea Academy, the Malta Leadership Institute and Pegaso International.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type². The HEIs included in ETER incorporate the University (*Università*), the College (*Kulleġġ*), the Academy (*Akkademja*) and the four Institutes (*Istitut*)³ of which two are private and two are public institutions. Up to 2020 within the ETER perimeter only the University of Malta and the Pegaso International award PhDs.⁴

¹ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/malta/types-higher-education-institutions>

² Institutional data reported in the ETER data collection depends on the perimeter as per ETER handbook. Furthermore, consent for inclusion of the institutions included in the perimeter is requested annually. Based on the perimeter and consent the number of HEIs covered may vary over time.

³ Throughout the whole report, the four Institutes are grouped within the HEI type Institute within the figures.

⁴ From 2021 onwards, the College also started offering PhDs.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Academy	Akkademja	1	0	1	0
College	Kulleġġ	1	1	0	0
Institute	Istitut	4	2	2	1
University	Università	1	1	0	1
Total		7	4	3	2

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

The first HEI in Malta was its only university, the University of Malta (L-Università ta' Malta), which was founded in 1769. The University stayed the only HEI for around two centuries until the Institute of Tourism Studies was established in 1987. Malta's College, the Malta College of Arts, Science & Technology were then founded in 2001, followed by the very recent establishment of the Institute for Education and the Pegaso International in 2015. The newest Institute, the Malta Leadership Institute was founded in 2017.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type of institution

Note: Foundation Year for the Academy is missing.

Students

Figure 2 shows the distribution of students by level and type of HEI for the year 2020 as reported in ETER. Overall, around 71% of all students in ISCED 5-7 attend Malta's University. The College is the second most attended HEI (17%), whereas around 9% of all students in ISCED 5-7 are enrolled in either of the four Institutes. As mentioned before, within ETER and up to 2020 the University and one of the Institutes are the only institutions which award PhDs. The University is also the only institution within ETER awarding Master long degrees. Furthermore, around 69% of all Bachelor and around 80% of all Master students (excluding Masters long degrees) attend Malta's University. The College is the institution with the second highest uptake in Bachelor degrees, followed by the Institutes. The Academy is attended mainly by Master students. Overall, the University is the most populated higher education institution in terms of the number of students in Malta.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER. Total students includes ISCED 5-7.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority. Similar to the number of students, Malta's University is also the main employer for academic personnel measured in full time equivalents (FTE). It is the only HEI employing research and teaching assistants (RTAs). Academic staff exceeds support and administrative personnel in Malta's College and the University. Only in one of the Institutes (Institute of Tourism Studies) does the number of support and administrative personnel exceed total academic personnel.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 4, in the University 7% of academic staff are foreign. Examining how this evolved over time, it is shown that this share has increased by around 3 percentage points since 2011.

Figure 4. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 5, in the year 2020, the University accounts for almost 78% of financial revenues of the whole HEI system considered in ETER whereas only about 76% of all academic personnel (in full-time equivalent, FTE) and 71% of all students are part of the University. Hence, the University seems to be the biggest institution in terms of students, revenues and academic personnel within ETER. In terms of size based on the three indicators shown in Figure 5, the University is followed by the College accounting for around 17% of total students, for around 14% of financial revenues and for around 19% of total academic personnel (FTE). For the Institutes and the Academy total students, total academic personnel (FTE) and financial resources make up less than 10% of the total. These institutions are thus the smallest.

Examining the composition of revenues, it is visible that the University of Malta is the only HEI receiving (research-related) third-party funds. Student fees play a minor role⁵ for the College and the Institutes. For the University they are as important as the third-party funds. Overall, state allocation remains dominant for the College, the University of Malta and the Institutes.

⁵ The Government of Malta funds undergraduate courses up to ISCED level 6 offered by the University of Malta (UOM), the Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology (MCAST) and the Institute of Tourism Studies (ITS) making these free of charge for Maltese and EU citizens. The Government of Malta also funds full-time postgraduate courses that lead to a professional warrant. (<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/malta/higher-education-funding>).

Figure 5. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER. Total students includes ISCED 5-7.

Figure 6. Composition of resources. 2020

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Changing roles over time

Presented in Figure 7, data show a stable evolution with slight fluctuations of the overall number of enrolled students (ISCED 5-7) for Malta's University and College between 2012 and 2020. The evolution of the number of students differs between the two HEIs. While the number of University students stayed relatively stable, increasing only by around 1.2% from 10.734 to 10.865 students between 2012 and 2020, the number of College students increased by almost 63% from 1588 to 2586 students in the same period of time.

Figure 7. Number of students (ISCED 5-7) enrolled by type of HEI, 2012-2020

Figure 8 showing the evolution of the number of academic personnel in head counts (HC) for the University and the College depicts an increasing pattern. Similar to the evolution of the number of students, the number of academic personnel in head counts employed in the College increases stronger compared to the University's academic personnel. While the number of personnel in the College almost tripled between 2012 and 2020 from 112 to 319 (+207) employees, the number of the University's academic personnel in head counts increased slightly less in terms of total number of employees from 1291 to 1456 (+165) employees.

Figure 8. Academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2012-2020

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